

Evidence-Based Toxicology

Declaration of Related Interests Form

This version: 23 January 2025

Guidance Notes

- (1) The purpose of this form is to support clear and comprehensive declaration of author interests in relation to journal submissions. Interests matter because they have the potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in a research project. Interests therefore need to be disclosed and, if they constitute a conflict of interest, they need to be managed.
- (2) An interest is any commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice that relates to the commitments, obligations, duties, or goals associated with the particular work being described in a submission to Evidence-Based Toxicology.
- (3) Related interests may be financial or non-financial. Declarations of related interests are essential in enabling editors and peer-reviewers to evaluate how effectively submitting authors have managed their interests in relation to their research goals.
- (4) Having or declaring a related interest is not the same thing as having a conflict of interest. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another interest. Conflicts of interest need to be managed by researchers in order to preserve the integrity of decision-making in a study.
- (5) Contributors to a research project should declare all related interests that a reasonable person would want to know about to be confident that the interests that relate to the submitted work are known about, and can therefore be evaluated for having been appropriately managed.
- (6) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.
- (7) Interests that cannot contractually be declared need not be described in detail, but their existence must be noted. If the contract specifies that not even the presence of a contractual limitation can be declared, the author should state they are unable to complete the form.

Author information

Name: Dr Eleni Iacovidou

Date: 11/02/2025

Title of manuscript: State of the evidence on the impacts of fishing plastic waste to coastal communities: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map

Contribution to the Publication

Please agree this with the senior authors and describe in CRediT format if possible

Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review & editing

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Interests

Please select "Yes" or "No" next to any interests below that are relevant to your situation

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by your submitted publication?		Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by your submitted publication?	
No	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	No	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
No	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	No	Current and previous research findings or projects
No	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	No	Commitments to specific standards or processes
No	From litigation or legal cases	No	Publicly held positions
No	From grants	No	Personal relationships
No	Other financial interests	No	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
		No	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you may be seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
		Yes	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Not relevant.

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The author declares no financial conflicts of interest. They have an active research interest in plastic-related studies and the application of systems-based approaches to addressing sustainability challenges. These academic and professional engagements may be perceived as potential influences, but they have not biased the research design, analysis, or conclusions.

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(3) Contributors to a research project should **declare** all interests that a reasonable person would want to know about to be confident that these interests are being appropriately managed. Declaring an interest is not the same thing as having a conflict of interest.

(4) A **conflict of interest** arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another interest. Conflicts of interest need to be managed by researchers in order to preserve the integrity of decision-making in a study.

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Author information

Name: Joanne McPhie

Date: 11/02/2025

Title of manuscript: State of the evidence on the impacts of fishing plastic waste to coastal communities: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map

Contribution to the Publication

Please agree this with the senior authors and describe in CRediT format if possible

Advice and collaboration on the development of a robust systematic search strategy and guidance on appropriate choice and usage of information sources.

Interests

Please select “Yes” or “No” next to any interests below that are relevant to your situation

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None

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None

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Author information

Name: Larisha Apete

Date: 11/02/2025

Title of manuscript: State of the evidence on the impacts of fishing plastic waste to coastal communities: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map

Contribution to the Publication

Please agree this with the senior authors and describe in CRediT format if possible

Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Validation, Writing - original draft, and Writing - review & editing

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Financial support was provided by Natural Environment Research Council (NERC).

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N/A

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Author information

Name: Olwenn Martin

Date: 11/02/2025

Title of manuscript: State of the evidence on the impacts of fishing plastic waste to coastal communities: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map

Contribution to the Publication

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Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review & editing.

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Beyond the current PhD scholarship offered for this project, I do not have any financial interest. My time is not funded under the present scholarship.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

The topic of current project is relevant to a UCL Climate Crisis Grand Challenge small grant I and others are receiving funding for. This does not include funding for our time.

I am a member of the Planetary Health Alliance, the Alliance Sante that will be interested in the topic of the impacts of fishing plastic waste and the results of the current project.

I am a member of the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration and an associate editor of the Evidence-Based Toxicology journal, both are committed to specific standards related to evidence synthesis.